

Syntheses and Growth Retardant Activities of Trialkylammonium Iodides from Piperonal

M. L. SHARMA*, J. L. KAPOOR, NIRUPMA SOOD, SATWINDER KAUR and P. S. KALSI

Department of Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana-141 004

Manuscript received 3 June 1985, revised 19 February 1986, accepted 18 June 1986

Eleven new trialkylammonium iodides were prepared from piperonal and were examined as plant growth retardants on the germination of turnip seeds. *N*-*n*-Butyl-*N,N*-dimethyl-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)methylammonium iodide (5) hitherto unknown was the effective growth retardant at higher concentration.

IN continuation of our previous work on syntheses and growth retardant activity of trialkylammonium compounds^{1,2}, in the present investigation, we studied eleven new trialkylammonium compounds derived from piperonal as growth retardants. The compound *N*-*n*-butyl-*N,N*-dimethyl-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)methylammonium iodide (5) was found to be as active as abscisic acid (ABA) at a concentration of 50 ppm, when tested on the germination of turnip seeds.

Dialkyl derivatives (2) and (15), prepared by subjecting the piperonal (1) and 3,4-methylenedioxyacetophenone (14) to Leuckarts-Wallach reaction with DMF and HCOOH³, were converted to the quaternary ammonium salts 3, 4, 5 and 16 by treating *N,N*-dimethyl-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)methylamine (2) and *N,N*-dimethyl-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)ethylamine (15) with the suitable alkylhalides. *N,N*-Diethyl-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)methylamine (6), *N,N*-diethyl-1-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)ethylamine (12) and *N,N*-diethyl-2-methyl-3-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)prop-2-enylamine (19) were prepared by heating piperonylbromide, 1-bromo-1-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)ethane (11) and 2-methyl-3-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)prop-2-ethyl bromide (18) with diethylamine and K₂CO₃ in dry acetone⁴, respectively.

The bromides (11) and (18) were in turn prepared by brominating 1-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)ethanol (10) and 2-methyl-3-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-ol (17) with PBr₃, respectively.

The dialkyl derivatives (6, 12 and 19) were then converted to the quaternary ammonium salts (7-9, 13 and 20-22) by the conventional procedure.

Growth retarding activities of the compounds thus obtained were examined on the germination of turnip seeds.

Experimental

Boiling and melting points are uncorrected. Unless otherwise stated, all organic extracts were dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Purity of samples was checked by tlc. Ir spectra (thin film) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 infrared spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (90 MHz) in CCl_4 on EM 360/390 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

2-Methyl-3-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)prop-2-enyl bromide (18): To a well stirred cooled solution of the alcohol (17: 5 g) in dry ether (30 ml) containing pyridine (1 ml) PBr_3 (1.3 ml) in dry ether (5 ml) was added dropwise, and reaction mixture stirred for another 2 h at room temperature. It was allowed to stand overnight, then refluxed for 2 h, cooled, decomposed with cold water and washed with saturated NaHCO_3 solution and water successively. Distillation of the solvent afforded the bromide (18; 5 g, 71.5%), ν_{max} 2910, 1640, 1440, 1040, 935, 885, 810, 790, 755 and 730 cm^{-1} . It was used as such in next operation.

1-(3'-4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl)ethylbromide (11): The alcohol (10; 2 g) in dry ether (15 ml) containing pyridine (1 ml) was treated with PBr_3 in dry ether (5 ml) as described above to afford the bromide (11; 2g, 72.5%); ν_{max} 2850, 1610, 1450, 1070, 920, 870, 805 and 750 cm^{-1} . The bromide thus obtained was used as such in the next operation.

N,N-Dimethylaminoderivatives (2 and 15): Piperonal (1.5 g), DMF (7.6 g) and formic acid (4.3 g, 85%) were refluxed at 190° on a oil-bath for 6 h. The pale yellow homogeneous solution after cooling was added slowly in 10% HCl solution (50 ml) and

the aqueous amine hydrochloride was extracted twice with ether. The aqueous phase was treated with 10% sodium hydroxide solution and the dimethylamino compound recovered by extracting with ethyl ether. After drying, it was distilled under reduced pressure to get the dimethylamine (2; 3 g, 60%), b.p. 99-100°/5-6 mm (Found: C, 67.11; H, 7.32; N, 7.82. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_2$ requires: C, 67.03; H, 7.26; N, 7.82%); δ 2.15 (6H, s, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.22 (2H, s, $\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 5.90 (2H, s, O- CH_2 -O), 6.68 (2H, bs, ArH) and 6.8 (1H, bs, ArH).

In a similar way, the dimethylamino derivative (15) was prepared by heating the ketone (14; 2 g), DMF (2.8 g) and formic acid (1.6 g, 85%) in a oil-bath for 15 h, (0.65 g, 27%) (Found: C, 68.29; H, 7.74; N, 7.29. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires: C, 68.39; H, 7.77; N, 7.25%); δ 1.3 (3H, d, J 7Hz, Ar- $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)$), 2.20 (6H, s, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.20 (1H, hump, Ar $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)\text{N}$), 6.0 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 6.80 (2H, bs, ArH) and 6.92 (1H, bs, ArH).

N,N-Diethylamino derivatives (6, 12 and 19): Priperonyl bromide (8 g), diethylamine (3.2 g), K_2CO_3 (4 g) and acetone (60 ml) were stirred at 60° for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then filtered and most of the acetone was removed by distillation. 10% HCl (150 ml) was then added and stirred. The solution was extracted with ether. Aqueous layer was then treated with 10% NaOH solution and extracted with ether. The ether extract was dried, ether removed and vacuum distilled to give the amine (2; 4.2 g, 53%), b.p. 102-103°/6-7 mm (Found: C, 69.48; H, 8.30; N, 6.83. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires: C, 69.56; H, 8.21; N, 6.76%); δ 1.10 (6H, t, J 7Hz, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.5 (4H, q, J 7Hz, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.48 (2H, s, Ar $\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2$), 5.98 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 6.78 (2H, bs, ArH) and 6.90 (1H, bs, ArH).

The diethylamino derivative (12) was prepared by taking the bromide (11; 1.7 g), diethylamine (0.6 g), K_2CO_3 (0.7 g) and acetone (10 ml) according to the method described above, (1.2 g, 72%), b.p. 95-97°/4-5 mm (Found: C, 70.62, H, 8.63, N, 6.26. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires; C, 70.58; H, 8.59; N,

TABLE 1—PERCENT GERMINATION OF TURNIP SEEDS IN DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF THE COMPOUNDS CONSIDERING CONTROL AS 100%

Compd. no.	Concentration (ppm)									
	(0.01)	(0.1)	(1.0)	(5.0)	(10.0)	(15.0)	(20.0)	(25.0)	(50.0)	
3	75.00	93.80	40.90	53.10	46.90	56.90	37.50	40.60	15.60	
4	68.80	93.80	53.10	18.80	25.00	34.40	40.60	50.30	18.80	
5	103.10	93.80	71.90	34.40	31.80	43.80	25.00	15.60	—	
7	72.20	94.40	66.70	50.00	27.80	38.90	33.30	50.00	38.90	
8	116.70	94.40	66.70	55.60	66.70	44.40	77.80	61.10	55.60	
9	110.71	96.56	62.13	62.16	68.70	40.20	80.20	59.00	45.40	
13	105.60	111.10	88.30	50.00	61.10	77.80	38.90	27.80	11.10	
16	102.00	90.00	92.50	60.00	52.00	72.60	30.00	27.80	9.00	
20	77.80	72.20	66.70	72.20	55.60	44.40	55.60	44.40	33.30	
21	100.00	87.50	84.40	43.80	40.60	56.30	34.40	31.90	21.90	
22	100.00	84.40	68.80	65.60	37.50	50.00	34.40	21.90	15.60	
ABA	84.20	65.80	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	

Water (control) = 100%.

6.33%); δ 1.02–1.10 (9H, N(CH₂CH₃)₂, ArCHCH₃), 2.48 (4H, q, N(CH₂CH₃)₂), 3.45 (1H, hump, ArCH(CH₃)N), 5.98 (2H, s, OCH₂O), 6.72 (2H, bs, ArH) and 6.87 (1H, bs, ArH).

Similarly, **19** was prepared by taking the bromide (**18**; 4.7 g), diethylamine (1.7 g), K₂CO₃ (1.8 g) and acetone (30 ml), (2.8 g, 56%), b.p. 150–52°/12–15 mm (Found: C, 72.80; H, 8.59; N, 5.72 – C₁₆H₂₁O₂N requires: C, 72.87; H, 8.50, N, 5.66%); δ 1.05 (6H, t, N(CH₃)₂), 1.85 (3H, s, ArCH=C–CH₃), 2.50 (4H, q, N(CH₂CH₃)₂), 3.0 (2H, s, ArCH=C(CH₃)CH₂N), 5.93 (2H, s, OCH₂O), 6.3 (1H, s, ArCH=C), 6.72 (2H, bs, ArH) and 6.75 (1H, bs, ArH).

General procedure for preparation of trialkylammonium iodides: Syntheses of *N,N,N*-trimethyl-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)methylammonium iodide (**3**) is shown as a typical run. To a cold (5°) solution of *N,N*-dimethyl-3-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)-methylamine (**2**; 1 g) in ether (15 ml) was added

dropwise, methyl iodide (1.6 g) and the mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature. It was allowed to stand at room temperature overnight, and the precipitate obtained by centrifugation yielded **3** (1.25 g, 73%), m.p. 220°. All quaternary salts of ammonia were prepared by treating the different *N,N*-dialkylamino compounds with suitable alkyl iodide according to the method as described above and the yield vary from 60–75%. The m.p. of compounds **3**, **4** and **7**, is > 220°, 131–33° and 138–40°, respectively, and gave satisfactory elemental analysis. All other compounds were so hygroscopic in nature that their m.p. and elemental analysis were not possible.

References

1. M. L. SHARMA, MD. BARAMAKI, K. K. TALWAR and P. S. KALSI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, **21**, 1049.
2. M. L. SHARMA, S. B. PANDHI, K. K. TALWAR and P. S. KALSI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1985, **24**, 571.
3. R. D. BACH, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, **33**, 1647.
4. R. K. MAHAJAN and M. M. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1978, **16**, 430.